

Effects of Service Quality on Clothing E-Commerce Customer Satisfaction and E-Brand Loyalty

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Abstract: With the expansion of technologies and increasing use of internet, the online market is blooming at a noticeable rate. Online Shopping is now a well-known term for the people of all ages. Businesses are constantly trying to find new strategies that can help them gain loyal customers, in order to avoid the considerable cost of attracting new customers. The competition among online companies is to increase sale by getting new customers, make their shopping cart full, and make customers repurchase. To do this companies need to have an idea on cluster of their target customer and customers' demand. The present study seeks to provide a deeper understanding of the brand experience phenomenon in online context by investigating the impact of e-brand experience on e-satisfaction and e-loyalty. This thesis analyzes if service quality has any significant impact on brand loyalty, where customer satisfaction is used as an indicator for brand loyalty. Furthermore, this thesis aims to measure the impact that service quality has on customer satisfaction, as well as if service quality has any significant effect on brand loyalty. This study also aspires to further explore the correlation between the different factors that cause a consumer to become loyal to a brand.

Keywords: Customer Satisfaction, Brand Loyalty, E-Commerce, E-SERVQUAL.

1. INTRODUCTION

Businesses round the world hunt for new and innovative ways that to amass additional customers and become additional undefeated financially. One amongst the key factors for a business to become undefeated is to possess content customers. Ninety-six of customers everywhere the world thinks about service quality to be a very important side of them selecting to be loyal to a whole. Seventieth of shoppers claim that they're loyal to brands as a result of their nice customer service. Fifty-two of customers state that they need bought extra product from a corporation just because they antecedently have skilled nice service quality from that company (Willot, 2020). These numbers indicate that many various factors, like service quality, client satisfaction and whole loyalty area unit all vital for a corporation to be profitable. What is more, a way to acquire and maintain factors like these still be an essential challenge for corporations nowadays, and has been for a protracted time. Online is that the flourishing marketplace for fashion because the variety of net user will increase yearly. In 2017, the quantity of net users was three.58 billion globally, a growth from one.02 million in 2005. As of March 2017, regarding 731 million net users were Chinese and 287 million were Americans (Kacen and Lee, 2002: 165). Thus, with the increasing variety of net users, there's a possible on-line fashion market globally. Globally retail e-commerce sales as forecasted to be doubly between 2016 and 2020. A survey on Apr twenty17 disclosed that quite forty p.c of American net users look on-line a couple of times monthly and 20 shopped on-line once during a week. Online sales solely in USA are accumulated from 287 billion in 2014 to 523 billion in 2020 (Bellenger and Korgaonkar, 1980; 78). Therefore, it's vital to outline the profile of on-line fashion consumers since there's a high on-line garment industry ptaotential globally.

In order to stay customers loyal to a particular whole, a corporation ought to use totally different promoting ways (Aminuddin and Shamsudin, 2020: 1). If customers area unit glad with a particular whole, the corporate won't have a retardant in setting a worth for the product as a result of glad customers area unit willing to get hold of it albeit it's slightly dearly-won because the customers assume that it's affordable with the nice quality product that the whole area unit commercialism and it also can increase the revenue of the organizations (Hamzah and Shamsudin, 2020: 1). Past researches (Ahmad et.al., 2020: 1, Nur et.al., 2020: 1) indicates that a whole can stand out from the others as a result of the nice impression given by the glad customers. Organization could haven't to place a great deal of energy to vie with the opposite wholes as a result of their customers have compete the role in creating everybody believe that your brand area unit serving smart product and services by recommending it to the new customers. What is more, it'll additionally leave organization with an honest whole image from the market regarding the whole. Past analysis additionally highlighted that customers' satisfaction is vital as a result of their loyalty would be a perfect and easiest method to enhance the whole and expand it to an even bigger market (Nurnatasha and Syafiqah 2020: 3). A key issue that influences consumers' selection of shops, and alternative service suppliers, is client service. As an example, many of us like better to back up sure stores, do their banking at a selected establishment, lodge in a particular edifice, erode sure restaurants, or take their garments to a selected storekeeper, etc., supported the amount of client service provided by that institution. This side of client service encompasses such factors because the level of responsiveness, friendliness, reliability, and promptness of staff. Another key side of client service that affects consumers' decisions of shops and repair suppliers is that the manner within which the vendor responds to client complaints. Many times, customers create their decisions based mostly not solely on the amount of service provided at the time of sale, however additionally on their perception of the amount of client service they'll expect to receive once the sale, ought to a retardant arise. As an example, several new automotive consumers like better to obtain from a selected franchise as a result of its name for prompt, reliable, and courteous service. Likewise, several customers back up sure retail stores as a result of they recognize that if they encounter any issues with a product the retail merchant can exchange the merchandise or refund their cash, with no queries asked. This side of client service is crucial to the long gain of a firm. Corporations that develop a name for systematically breakdown client complaints area unit additional possible to develop client loyalty and, over time, could increase their market share. Conversely, corporations that develop a name for not being willing to remedy their customers' complaints could slowly lose several of their customers (Jeffrey et. al, 1995: 33).

2. SERVICE QUALITY AND CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

Many studies have established the link between service quality and client satisfaction. Firms and organizations attempt exhausting to realize high client satisfaction, particularly those firms that think about a semi-permanent relationship with customers as Associate in Nursinging quality. However, understanding the service quality parts stay to be a subject matter of discussions and arguments. Thus, perceived service quality has been wide thought of as Associate in Nursinging antecedent of client satisfaction and former studies have determined its relationship (Naik et al., 2010: 201; Yee et al., 2011: 237). However, there are still arguments and disagreements on the causative relationship between the 2 variables as applied in numerous settings. Customer satisfaction is usually outlined because the customers' post-purchase comparison between pre-purchase expectation and performance received (Oliver, 1980: 461). The link between service quality and client satisfaction has been mentioned in varied previous papers throughout the past decade. 1st of all, several researchers gift that service quality has positive connected relationship with client satisfaction. In different words, service quality influence client satisfaction and the other way around client satisfaction influence quality. There's little question that within the world's these days intensive competition, once a business desires to survive, they need to enhance the service quality that helps them to realize a unique advantage over their rivalries. Service quality, thus has become one amongst of the important factors for satisfying Associate in Nursinging retentive valued customers in every industries and banking isn't an exception. Several students indicate that top service quality leads to client satisfaction and loyalty with the merchandise or service. A glad client can have the temperament to suggest some other person, reduction in complaints and also the bank can do the client retention. Moreover, a glad client is probably going to be a loyal client UN agency can offer continuance business to the firm. The value of retentive existing client by rising the standard of product and services is looked as if it would be considerably less than the value of achieving the new customers.

On the opposite hand, once relating to the link between service quality and client satisfaction in some industries as banking, some students illustrate that service quality isn't associated with client satisfaction underneath sure circumstances. As an example, through varied studies, Parasuraman et al. (1985) indicated that despite the fact that customers were happy with a selected service, they failed to assume that it had been of prime quality. Another scholar conjointly agrees with this idea, A client might, therefore, respond on a form that a selected bank is of prime quality, though this failed to mean this client was

happy with victimization the bank. Its interest rates on loans could also be too high or it'd not match the customer's preferences for a few alternative reasons. E-service quality could be a service provided to customers by victimization the web. Service supported the web makes customers feel additional economical in playacting transactions in terms of your time and value. Accessibility of knowledge associate degreed sleek dealings is a possibility for purchasers to interact through the provision of system facilities and adequate net network also because the guarantee of information confidentiality. Excellent service quality is that the basis of client satisfaction. We tend to several sometimes realize a positive relationship between service quality, satisfaction, and loyalty. Thus, the e-service quality provided by the corporate can satisfy or not satisfy the client as a result of the standard services provided by the corporate have an effect on the amount of client satisfaction (Komara and Ariningrum, 2013). For on-line businesses, the e-service quality element should be created to create on-line client satisfaction (e-satisfaction) (Widiaputri et al., 2018: 2). Supported analysis conducted by Tobagus, (2018) on the web store website, e-service quality influences e-satisfaction. This relationship was found to own a positive and vital impact, with smart e-service quality having a major impact E-Satisfaction And E-Trust towards e-satisfaction. This can be in line with analysis conducted by Della Prisanti (2017: 30) indicating a positive relationship between e-service quality and e-satisfaction. The results of analysis by Widiaputri et al. (2018: 8) on Go-Ride customers expressed that e-service quality had a major impact on e-satisfaction.

2.1 Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty

Evidence showed that there's a major relationship between client satisfaction and client loyalty (Leninkumar, 2017: 459). Client loyalty is considered a results of client satisfaction, once customers who have sensible experiences with the service of the corporate can still take care of the corporate viewing it as less risky, thereby creating them loyal and rational in decision-making. In fact, several authors have advocated that client satisfaction is one amongst the determinates of client loyalty, particularly within the industry (Belas and Gabčov., 2016: 133; Coelho and Henseler, 2012: 341). In step with Munari et al. (2013: 141), satisfaction and loyalty square measure the parts of final loyalty, and satisfaction is that the place to begin of loyalty. What is more, it is assumed that the link between client satisfaction and client loyalty is nonlinear. Suggestions from Heskett et al. (2008: 125) got wind the importance of companies to extend the amount of client satisfaction if they need to sustain the amount of client loyalty. There is a positive relationship between client satisfaction and loyalty customers. Once a client is happy with a web site, they'll be willing to move a lot of with the location within the future and become loyal customers (Fang, Chiu, and Wang, 2011: 1). E-trust is outlined because the level of client trust in on-line exchange channels, failure in on-line retail is caused by a scarcity of shopper trust in electronic channels, so e-trust is thought of as a very important variable in shaping loyalty (Ghane et al., 2011: 3). Supported the results of analysis conducted by Asih and Pratomo, (2018: 137) on on-line searching activities administered by girls expressed that e-trust contains a positive and vital result on loyalty, the results of this study square measure in line with analysis conducted by Choi and Mai, (2018: 291) on B2C e-commerce in Vietnam that conjointly states that e-trust contains a positive and vital result on e-loyalty. Analysis conducted by Hasanudin, et.al., (2017: 80) on users of e-commerce services on the island of Java states that e-trust contains a positive and vital result on e-loyalty.

2.2 E-Service Quality And E-Loyalty

E-service quality is one amongst the ways or techniques measure of web site service quality supported user perceptions. In step with Rowley, e-service quality is associate degree act, effort or performance whose delivery is mediate by data technology. E-service sensible quality supported the prevailing literature that literature satisfaction with electronic media are going to be determined by the standard perceived from e-service quality that results in client satisfaction. Sensible e-service quality is to supply sensible service so shoppers feel safe and trust the location, so it will increase client trust as a result of trust is a very important think about business-customer interactions so it'll produce client loyalty to a web web site (Berlianto, 2018: 505). This theory supports analysis conducted by Purnamasari, (2018) shows that e-trust will mediate the result of e-service quality on e-loyalty. Analysis conducted by Nurayni and Widiartanto, (2019: 133) expressed that there's associate degree indirect result between e-service quality on e-loyalty through e-trust, wherever eservice quality trust is in a position to extend the influence of the e-service quality variable in influencing e-loyalty.

2.3 Why E-Sq?

Insights from studies handling people-technology interactions imply that client analysis of latest technologies could be a distinct method. For example, findings from an intensive qualitative study of however customers move with, and measure, technology-based product (Mick and Fournier 1995) recommend that (a) client satisfaction with such product involves a extremely complicated, meaning-laden, semipermanent process; (b) the method may vary across completely different client

segments; and (c) satisfaction in such contexts isn't invariably a perform of pre-consumption comparison standards. Another major qualitative study by identical authors (Mick and Fournier 1998: 47), that specialize in people's reactions to technology, suggests that technology might trigger positive and negative feelings at the same time. Moreover, different analysis involving each qualitative and empirical parts demonstrate that customers' propensity to embrace new technologies (i.e., their technology readiness) depends on the relative dominance of positive and negative feelings in their overall technology beliefs (Parasuraman 2000 : 307). Different analysis shows that perceived quality and easy use ar related considerably with self-reported (Davis 1989: 39) and actual (Szajna 1996: 87) usage of technology. Jointly, the findings of those studies reveal vital variations in acceptance and usage of technologies across customers looking on their technology beliefs and recommend that similar variations may exist within the critical processes employed in judgment e-SQ. In different words, customer-specific attributes (e.g., technology readiness) may influence, for example, the attributes that customers need in a perfect internet site and also the performance levels that may signal superior e-SQ. Overall. Providing sensible product and services is vital to stay the client satisfy. Client satisfaction plays a very important role as they assist business to run the business swimmingly in an exceedingly longer amount of your time. Client satisfaction in obtaining correct product and services will result organizations in obtaining a correct revenue and it will offer the business a chance to expand globally. Based on the examination of previous literature, these hypotheses were constructed:

H1: SERVQUAL has a positive effect on customer satisfaction

H2: SERVQUAL has a positive effect on brand loyalty

H3: Customer satisfaction features a positive influence on brand

H4: There is a relationship between customer satisfaction and loyalty.

3. METHODOLOGY

The E-S-QUAL Scale which is a Likert-type scale format for collecting responses (Parasuraman et. al. 2005). The questionnaire will consist of 22 items with 5-point scales ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The E-S-QUAL Scale will have 22 items on four dimensions, which will be labeled and defined as follows:

- Efficiency: The ease and speed of accessing and using the site.
- Fulfillment: The extent to which the site's promises about order delivery and item availability are fulfilled.
- System availability: The correct technical functioning of the site.
- Privacy: The degree to which the site is safe and protects customer information.

4. DISCUSSION

Businesses have begun out to perform their industrial sports in digital environments with the emergence of digital commerce. The diversification of the products/offering provided to purchasers within the digital surroundings and the growth within the quantity of organizations on this discipline make it crucial to supply pleasant carrier. Thanks to technology, purchasers can examine the product/carrier they buy from any enterprise in digital surroundings with every other enterprise, and in the event that they do now no longer locate it pleasant, they should buy carrier from every other enterprise. That is why it will become crucial for organizations to offer offerings with the aid of using satisfying the necessities of the digital surroundings and with the aid of using figuring out what elements' purchasers pay interest to (Faiz, 2018). The pleasant factors sought with the aid of using the purchasers within the offerings furnished in conventional environments fluctuate from the pleasant knowledge of the purchasers in on-line environments. For this reason, it's miles vital to degree the pleasant of the carrier that organizations offer at the internet.

Electronic trade (e-trade) refers back to the procedure of wearing out commercial enterprise among firms and clients the usage of digital medium along with internet. Companies are significantly the usage of this income channel to compete with their competition within the e-commerce marketplace. Business to Consumer (B2C) is one of the natures of transactions in e-trade. B2C refers to e-commerce version wherein companies promote to person consumers. The B2C on line marketplace has been developing hastily during the last numerous years and clients are more and more desired on line buying. Electronic carrier first-rate (e-SQ) is more and more vital in influencing purchaser opinions and judgments concerning the first-rate of e-carrier transport within the digital marketplace. Online buying in B2C entails on line consumers getting access to the web vendors' web sites to buy a product; consequently, the quantity to which their desires are fulfilled is vital (Ong et.al., 2016).

According to Anderson and Srinivasan (2003), e-pride is defined because the gratification of the purchaser that comes from his or her in advance actual shopping for enjoy with a positive digital trade company. It changed into empirically mounted that the human associated elements of perceived carrier first-rate (reliability, responsiveness, warranty and empathy), has a more effect on purchaser pride than that of the non-human associated elements of perceived carrier first-rate (tangibles, carrier capabilities and price) on Customer Satisfaction (Rahman et.al 2022).

As e-commerce websites are growing daily, customers can effortlessly navigate e-commerce web sites, locate the goods they want and carry out their transactions quickly. Also, due to the fact e-commerce web sites are more and more comparable and meet precise standards, a consumer who makes use of an e-commerce web website online can effortlessly locate what he/she is searching out while he/she enters some other e-commerce website online. These elements display that the performance measurement does now no longer have an effect on e-pride (Çelik 2021). The privateness measurement is ready defensive non-public records, storing credit score card records, and preserving the behaviour styles inside web website online. Privacy has constantly been a crucial detail in influencing patron behaviour. In unsure surroundings along with Internet-primarily based totally e-commerce transactions, the problem of privateness turns into even greater critical. The key to achievement in e-commerce web sites relies upon on clients' feeling secure at the same time as buying. Therefore, E-commerce web sites must specify what records is gathered from customers and the way these records might be used within the scope in their privateness policies. Also, previous consent must be acquired from the clients for capability non-public information transfers, and a way to touch the patron for applicable records sharing must be declared. The pattern of this examine is the clients of hepsiburada.com. The findings display that the web website online satisfied its customers that they may absolutely defend purchaser records via way of means of imparting dependable surroundings and that the records acquired will stay confidential. Users who're satisfied of this said that the privateness measurement does now no longer have an effect on e-pride (Çelik 2021).

In current years, carrier high-satisfactory and e-carrier high-satisfactory have turn out to be one of the maximum vital studies regions in advertising due to their considerable effect on a company's monetary performance. The high-satisfactory of digital offerings is shaped with the aid of using 5 dimensions, specifically privateness, responsiveness, ease of use, reliability, and efficiency. These 5 dimensions concurrently form carrier high-satisfactory in order that it may be measured and used to evaluate its impact on consumer pleasure and consumer loyalty (Luh et.al., 2022). It seems that once the pandemic, clients had been more and more more the usage of on-line systems for getting items and offerings (Zygiaris et.al., 2022). Customers understand the carrier high-satisfactory as a primary carrier expectation and could now no longer endure the greater price for this criterion. Precisely, the expertise approximately the clients' view regarding carrier high-satisfactory may be utilized by businesses as a device to enhance their consumer offerings. The Zygiaris et.al., (2022) of this study imply a robust affiliation among SERVQUAL dimensions and perceived carrier high-satisfactory.

The observation suggests that brand enjoy has high quality results on brand pleasure, accept as true with and loyalty. Brand enjoy creates and develops accept as true with-primarily based totally courting platform among brand and consumer. Brand reports rise up in a whole lot of settings while clients seek for, keep for, and eat brands. As Azize et.al (2011) effects show, brand pleasure has a extensively high quality have an impact on brand loyalty. Satisfaction with the favored brand is one of the determinants of brand loyalty. A customer who trusts within the brand is extra inclined to stay unswerving to it, to pay a top rate for it, to shop for new merchandise added beneath it within the current and in new categories, and to percentage a few statistics approximately his or her tastes, preferences, and behavior (Chaudhuri and Holbrook, 2001). In mild of the above, the remaining marketer's intention in brand-courting improvement is a consumer who's unswerving toward the brand. Website layout and security/privateness had nearly the identical effect on e-carrier high-satisfactory. Customer pleasure and consumer accept as true with regarded because the results of standard e-carrier high-satisfactory within the model. The effects of this observe confirmed that e-carrier high-satisfactory had a high-quality effect on consumer pleasure. The majority of studies accomplished approximately e-carrier high-satisfactory states that consumer pleasure is the principle determinant impacting on e-carrier high-satisfactory. It helps the concept that there may be a considerable courting among e-carrier high-satisfactory and consumer pleasure. E-carrier high-satisfactory additionally had a high-quality effect on consumer accept as true with. The higher the e-carrier high-satisfactory of a company, the better the consumer accept as true with. Providing properly carrier high-satisfactory complements consumer pleasure and consumer accept as true with. The research determined that consumer pleasure had a high-quality effect on repurchase intention, word-of-mouth, and placement revisit.

5. CONCLUSION

E-commerce is digital trade wherein shopping for and promoting sports are finished through a digital network. Good carrier high-satisfactory can appeal to clients to make purchases on-line. Low high-satisfactory will motive consumer dissatisfaction. Efforts to enhance the carrier high-satisfactory device may be plenty extra powerful for enterprise continuity. These development efforts will make purchasers extra dependable to the enterprise. In short, it may be stated that once carrier to purchasers is precise, it'll result in consumer delight and is predicted to shape purchaser loyalty to merchandise or offerings. The findings provide perception for managers to higher apprehend how eservice high-satisfactory is shaped and the way essential every characteristic and measurement of e-carrier high-satisfactory is to make certain consumer delight and agree with, which in the long run can assist to preserve on-line clients. Managers can enhance the carrier high-satisfactory of on-line shops primarily based totally at the outcomes of this studies and integrate it with the current marketplace trends. Managers must cautiously keep in mind the attributes of e-carrier high-satisfactory to increase their on-line shops. To offer advanced carrier high-satisfactory, agencies must offer an great web site design that includes enough information, visually attractive content, clean to make payments, clean to examine text, provide a few reductions and/or promotions, and short loading capacity. Beyond that, agencies need to make certain the timeliness of shipping and make certain the clients' facts safety and privacy. Managers must consciousness on web site design, safety/privacy, and achievement. Managers can rent a internet site fashion dressmaker to create appealing websites. Since achievement had the very best effect on usual carrier high-satisfactory, managers need to ensure that the product is introduced in precise situation and in the promised time. Having partnerships with numerous shipping courier offerings and letting clients select which one they need is probably a very good idea. Managers must input into agreements with shipping offerings if merchandise are damaged in the course of the shipping, determine which birthday celebration must be answerable for damage, so it does now no longer damage consumer delight and agree with. Since consumer delight and consumer agree with appreciably have an effect on consumer behavior, managers must contain it into their advertising and marketing strategy. Online shops normally have comments functions on their websites. An enterprise can give a boost to WOM motion through providing "percentage comments to buddies" functions. After clients obtain the coolest they ordered, they could write comments on the net keep internet site. Moreover, delight is an essential component within the eyes of purchasers as clients will now no longer be dependable to the net store until they're happy first. Customers have the choice to percentage they enjoy with their buddies as WOM motion. Small rewards like unique reductions within the subsequent buy will inspire clients to unfold their shopping for enjoy to others, that could deliver extra ability clients to go to a enterprise's on-line keep.

Despite the dramatic upward thrust and fall of Internet businesses, e-commerce has validated non-stop boom in sales. E-commerce has great implications for the businesses and clients concerned in addition to society at large. For businesses, e-commerce can enhance performance and productivity. Furthermore, e-commerce permits personnel to have extra get entry to statistics and offerings, that can assist to keep a healthful company culture. For clients, e-commerce presents a completely handy manner to transact many styles of enterprise 24 hours a day, 7 days a week. For society, e-commerce can assist to boost up their monetary boom and opportunities, however on the equal time might also additionally pose demanding situations and issues in phrases of surveillance and privacy. The burst of the dot-com bubble might also additionally genuinely have delivered approximately a extra rational and sustainable technique to e-trade. However, as e-commerce grows, we can maintain to witness adjustments within the manner human beings conceive of organizations, transactions, and communications with a dramatic rethinking of time and area issues in monetary activities. These findings endorse to the web keep corporations they want to offer fine of e-offerings that fulfill the expectancies of clients. Online keep corporations additionally want to take interest to the size of e-provider fine that are essential from clients' factor of view as now no longer all dimensions are essential. Online keep corporations have to decide and consciousness in this essential element in constructing their competitiveness. This locating is delivered to the advanced expertise of e-provider fine and truly contributed to the sensible factors of on-line corporations. Nowadays, businesses must take motion in line with the desires of the purchasers, now no longer their very own desires. Companies must try this so as to benefit extra purchaser and live competitive. This scenario presents the purchasers with exclusive options even as making their choices, making it less difficult to assess the options, to look and make a desire to attain all styles of statistics approximately the desired product or provider. Today, with the improvement of technology, diverse social media and verbal exchange tools, client attention approximately services and products and the extent of client statistics approximately those services and products have extended considerably. Therefore, entrepreneurs have to intently screen variations in shopping conduct of purchasers and form their advertising and marketing techniques accordingly. Many elements can have an effect on the client's desire approximately the product and/or provider. Product fine, brand attention, perceived price, provider fine etc. Factors together with can have an effect on each the shopping conduct of the client and the hobby and notion of the product. The truth that

the loyalty of the purchaser is affected definitely or negatively in line with the perceived price of the brand is a trouble that corporations have to consciousness on sensitively.

5.1 Recommendations

The globalizing economic system affords extra possibilities for e-commerce. The international Internet populace is extra diverse than ever before. As one of the maximum influential monetary paperwork in our age, vast studies will retain to awareness on e-commerce. Historical and monetary research will take a look at the effect of the evolution of the infrastructures, technologies, strategies, and law of e-commerce. With the fast improvement of world e-commerce, destiny studies will don't forget implications of improvements in international telecommunications, cell communications in addition to the have an impact on of cross-cultural content material and practices. In general, those findings need to be replicated with one-of-a-kind product classes and brands. Also, the existing take a look at did now no longer take a look at private factors, brand involvement, brand institutions and brand personality. Overall, we nonetheless want to increase an extra unique information of the connection among brand loyalty and different dating advertising associated variables. Further studies need to awareness at the antecedents and long-time period effects of brand experiences.

REFERENCES

- [1] A.L. Abdul Rahman, A.R. Mohamed Akram and M. Siraj, 2022. Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction: Evidence from State Commercial Banks in Ampara District, Sri Lanka. *Daengku: Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Innovation*, 2(1): 9–18
- [2] Aminuddin, M., Don, M., and Shamsudin, M. F. (2020). DOES CUSTOMER SATISFACTION MATTERS ? *Journal of Undergraduate Social Science and Technology*, 2(1).
- [3] Anderson, R.E. and Srinivasan, S.S. (2003). E-satisfaction and e-loyalty: a contingency framework. *Psychology and Marketing*, 20(2), 123-138.
- [4] Asih, R. R. D., and Pratomo, L. A. (2018). Peran mediasi e-satisfaction dan e-trust terhadap e-loyalty. *Jurnal Manajemen dan Pemasaran Jasa*, 11(1), 125-144.
- [5] Azize Sahin, Cemal Zehir and Hakan Kitap (2011). The Effects of Brand Experiences, Trust and Satisfaction on Building Brand Loyalty; An Empirical Research On Global Brands. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences* 24 (2011) 1288–1301.
- [6] Bashir Ahmad Fida, Umar Ahmed, Yousuf Al-Balushi and Dharmendra Singh (2020). Impact of Service Quality on Customer Loyalty and Customer Satisfaction in Islamic Banks in the Sultanate of Oman. *SAGE Open*, pp 1–10. DOI: 10.1177/2158244020919517
- [7] Belas, J., and Gabčov., L. (2016). The relationship among customer satisfaction, loyalty and financial performance of commercial banks. *EandM Economics and Management*, 19(1), 132–147.
- [8] Berlianto, M. P. (2019). Identifying Antecedents and Consequences of Customer Satisfaction in the Full-Service Airline Industry. *Jurnal Manajemen*, 23(3), 496-510.
- [9] Bellenger DN, Korgaonkar PK (1980) Profiling the recreational shopper. *J Retailing* 56(3): 77-92.
- [10] Çelik, K., The effect of e-service quality and after-sales e-service quality on e-satisfaction, *bmij* (2021) 9 (3): 1137-1155, doi: <https://doi.org/10.15295/bmij.v9i3.1898>
- [11] Chaudhuri Arjun, Holbrook B. Moris, (2001), "The Chain of Effects From Brand Trust and Brand Affects to Brand Performance: The Role of Brand Loyalty", *Journal of Marketing* Vol.65, p.81-93
- [12] Choi, Y., and Mai, D. Q. (2018). The sustainable role of the e-trust in the B2C e-commerce of Vietnam. *Sustainability*, 10(1), 291.
- [13] Coelho, P. S., and Henseler, J. (2012). Creating customer loyalty through service customization. *European Journal of Marketing*, 46(3– 4), 331–356. <https://doi.org/10.1108/03090561211202503>
- [14] Davis, Fred D. (1989), "Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use and User Acceptance of Information Technology," *MIS Quarterly*, 13 (3), 318-39.

- [15] Della Prisanti, M. (2017). Pengaruh E-Service Quality Dan E-Trus Terhadap E-Customer Satisfaction Serta Implikasinya Terhadap Ecustomer Loyalty. *Journal of Business Studies*, 2(1), 19-38.
- [16] Faiz, E. (2018), "The Effect of Service Quality of Online Travel Shopping on the E-Satisfaction and E-Loyalty", *Electronic Journal of Social Sciences*, 17(68).
- [17] Fang, Y. H., Chiu, C. M., and Wang, E. T. (2011). Understanding customers' satisfaction and repurchase intentions: An integration of IS success model, trust, and justice. *Internet research*.
- [18] Ghane, S. O. H. E. I. L. A., Fathian, M., and Gholamian, M. R. (2011). Full relationship among e-satisfaction, e-trust, e-service quality, and e-loyalty: The case of Iran e-banking. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology*, 33(1), 1-6.
- [19] Hamzah, A. A., Shamsudin, M. F. (2020). Why Customer Satisfaction Is Important. *Journal of Undergraduate Social Science and Technolog*, 2(1). Retrieved from <http://blog.clientheartbeat.com/why-customer-satisfaction-is-important/>
- [20] Hasanuddin, R., and Sjahrudin, H. (2017). The structure of emotional intelligence, spiritual intelligence and its relationship with work enthusiasm and auditor performance. *Structure*, 3(1), 67-85.
- [21] Heskett, J. L., Jones, T. O., Loveman, G. W., Sasser, W. E., Jr., and Schlesinger, L. A. (2008). Putting the service-profit chain to work. *Harvard Business Review*, 86, 118–129.
- [22] Jeffrey G. Blodgett Kirk L. Wakefield James H. Barnes, (1995),"The effects of customer service on consumer complaining behavior", *Journal of Services Marketing*, Vol. 9 Iss 4 pp. 31 – 42. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/08876049510094487>
- [23] Kacen JJ, Lee JA (2002) The influence of culture on consumer impulsive buying behavior. *Journal of Consumer Psychology* 12(2): 163-176.
- [24] Komara, A., and Ariningrum, H. (2013). Analisis faktor-faktor yang mempengaruhi kinerja sistem informasi akuntansi. *Jurnal Riset Akuntansi Dan Manajemen*, 2(1), 2.
- [25] Leninkumar, V. (2017). The relationship between customer satisfaction and customer trust on loyalty. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 7, 450–464.
- [26] Mick, David Glenn and Susan Fournier (1995), "Technological Consumer Products in Everyday Life: Ownership, Meaning, and Satisfaction," working paper, report No. 95-104, 1-59, Marketing Science Institute, Cambridge, MA
- [27] Mick, David Glenn and Susan Fournier (1998), "Paradoxes of Technology: Consumer Cognizance, Emotions, and Coping Strategies," *Journal of Consumer Research*, 25 (September), 123-47.
- [28] Munari, L., Ielasi, F., and Bajetta, L. (2013). Customer satisfaction management in Italian banks. *Qualitative Research in Financial Markets*, 5(2), 139–160
- [29] Naik, C. N. K., Gantasala, S. B., and Prabhakar, G. V. (2010). SERVQUAL, customer satisfaction and behavioural intentions in retailing. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 17(2), 200–213.
- [30] Nurayni, D., and Widiartanto, W. (2019). PENGARUH E-SERVICE QUALITY, E-SATISFACTION DAN E-TRUST TERHADAP CUSTOMER LOYALTY PENGGUNA APLIKASI MOBILE KAI ACCESS (Studi pada pengguna Aplikasi Mobile KAI Acces Semarang). *Jurnal Ilmu Administrasi Bisnis*, 8(2), 128-137.
- [31] Nurnatasha Mohd Yussoff and Syafiqah Md Nayan (2020). Review on customer satisfaction. *Journal of Undergraduate Social Science and Technology* Vol. 2 No. 2, pp 1-6.
- [32] Nur, N., Nik, S., and Shamsudin, M. F. (2020). The Power of Reciprocity Theory in Marketing. *Journal of Postgraduate Current Business Research*, 5(1).
- [33] Oliver, R.L., 1980. A Cognitive model of the Antecedents and Consequences of satisfaction decisions. *J. Market. Res.* 17 (4), 460–469. November.
- [34] Ong Soo Ting, Mohd Shoki Md Ariff, Norhayati Zakuan, Zuraidah Sulaiman and Muhamad Zamari Mat Saman, (2016). E-Service Quality, E-Satisfaction and E-Loyalty of Online Shoppers in Business to Consumer Market; Evidence form Malaysia. *IOP Conf. Series: Materials Science and Engineering* 131, pp 1-10

- [35] Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V., and Berry, L. (1985). A Conceptual Model of Service Quality and Its Implications for Future Research. *Journal Of Marketing*, 49(4), 41-50. doi: 10.2307/1251430
- [36] Parasuraman, A. (2000), "Technology Readiness Index (TRI): A Multiple Item Scale to Measure Readiness to Embrace New Technologies," *Journal of Services Research*, 2 (4), 307-20.
- [37] Purnamasari, D. (2018, October). The Roles of E-Service Quality, E-Trust, and E-Satisfaction on Online Retail Loyalty. In *Prosiding Industrial Research Workshop and National Seminar* (Vol. 9, pp. 633-641).
- [38] Szajna, Bernadette (1996), "Empirical Evaluation of the Revised Technology Acceptance Model," *Management Science*, 42 (1), 85-92.
- [39] Tobagus, A. (2018). Pengaruh E-Service Quality Terhadap E-Satisfaction Pada Pengguna Di Situs Tokopedia. *Agora*, 6(1).
- [40] Widiaputri, Y. S., Suharyono, S., and Bafadhal, A. S. (2018). Pengaruh E-Service Quality Terhadap Perceived Value Dan ECustomer Satisfaction (Survei Pada Pelanggan Go-Ride Yang Menggunakan Mobile Application Go-Jek Di Kota Malang). *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis*, 61(1), 1-10.
- [41] Willott, L. (2020). Customer Service Stats for 2020. Retrieved 15 March 2020, from <https://www.customerthermometer.com/customer-service/customerservice-and-satisfaction-statistics-for-2020/>
- [42] Yee, R. W. Y., Yeung, A. C. L., and Cheng, T. C. E. (2011). The service- profit chain: An empirical analysis in high-contact service industries. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 130(2), 236–245.
- [43] Zygiaris S, Hameed Z, Ayidh Alsubaie M and Ur Rehman S (2022) Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction in the Post Pandemic World: A Study of Saudi Auto Care Industry. *Front. Psychol.* 13:842141. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2022.842141